

DEVELOPMENT OF WRITTEN SPEECH SKILLS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN HIGHER GRADES

¹Alisher Rustamov Abduhakimovich, ²Norqulova Dilrabo Sarvar qizi

¹A teacher at the Department of Integrated English Language course in Samarkand State Institute
of Foreign Languages

²A student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

¹ +998933380034

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10827393>

Abstract. *This article explores the growth of written speech abilities in upper-level foreign language instruction, emphasizing practical methods and techniques for enhancing students' writing ability. The paper examines important ideas, approaches, and tools for encouraging students' writing development in the target language, drawing on research in second language writing, pedagogy, and language education. Focusing on the significance of the writing process, real-world assignments, language precision and fluency, reference materials, incorporating technology, critical thinking, and introspection, the paper offers helpful advice for teachers looking to improve the way they teach written communication in foreign language classes.*

Keywords: *written speech skills, foreign language instruction, higher grades, language proficiency, writing development, writing process, authentic tasks, language accuracy, language fluency, model texts, technology integration, critical thinking, reflection, second language writing, pedagogy, language education.*

Introduction.

In higher grades, developing written speech abilities is an essential part of learning a foreign language. Students who are proficient in writing are able to interact with a variety of audiences in the target language, communicate complex ideas, and express themselves clearly. The teaching of written expression rises to prominence in language classrooms as educators work to develop students' communicative and linguistic competence.

This article examines the complex process of helping higher-grade students learn written speech in foreign languages. We look at the guiding ideas, methods, and materials that support students' growth as writers in the target language, drawing on research, best practices, and pedagogical insights. We explore the fundamental elements of successful writing instruction, including comprehending the writing process, incorporating real-world tasks, developing language accuracy and fluency, using model texts, utilizing technology, stimulating critical thinking, and promoting reflection.

Proficiency in written communication is becoming more and more important in today's multicultural and interconnected world as a means of achieving success in the workplace, in school, and in personal life. Therefore, teachers are essential in helping students along their path to becoming competent and self-assured writers in the language of instruction. Teachers enable students to navigate a variety of linguistic and cultural contexts, articulately express their ideas, and participate meaningfully in the global community by providing them with the skills, strategies, and support networks they need.

This article seeks to give educators useful insights and doable tactics for improving the development of written speech skills in higher-grade foreign language instruction through an examination of successful practices and cutting-edge methodologies. Teachers can create dynamic

and engaging learning environments that motivate students to become proficient and effective writers in the target language by adopting a learner-centered and communicative approach to writing instruction.

1. Stress Writing Process:

It is crucial to stress the writing process, which entails pre-writing, drafting, revising, editing, and publishing, when teaching foreign languages to upper-level students (Flower & Hayes, 1981; Zamel, 1983). Before starting to write their written texts, encourage students to organize, brainstorm, and create an outline. Give students the chance to self-evaluate, attend teacher conferences, and receive peer feedback in order to assist their writing development.

2. Integrate Realistic Writing Tasks:

According to Swales (1990) and Johns (1997), include realistic writing tasks and genres that correspond to real-world communicative contexts and objectives. Students can practice writing for a variety of audiences, genres, and rhetorical situations through assignments like emails, letters, essays, reports, articles, and creative writing projects. Students learn genre awareness, register variation, and rhetorical techniques—all necessary for clear written communication—through authentic writing assignments.

3. Focus on Language Fluency and Accuracy:

Provide opportunities for meaningful communication and controlled practice to strike a balance between language fluency and accuracy in writing instruction (Ellis, 2008; Bygate, 2001). Provide students with scaffolded writing exercises that focus on particular language elements including syntax, vocabulary, sentence structure, and punctuation while also fostering their ability to communicate clearly and imaginatively. Students should be encouraged to take chances, play around with language, and experiment with various writing registers and styles.

4. Provide Model Texts and Writing Models:

Students' writing development can be aided by exposure to model texts and writing models, which are useful tools (Hyland, 2003; Williams, 2005). Examine and talk about model texts that show good writing techniques, structuring patterns, and language usage norms. To help students grasp writing conventions and rhetorical strategies, model the writing process through think-alouds, demonstrations, and group writing exercises.

5. Use Technology and Digital Tools:

According to Warschauer (2006) and Levy & Stockwell (2006), use technology and digital tools to improve writing instruction and offer opportunities for real-world writing practice. To encourage students to write, promote peer collaboration, and display their writing portfolios, use word processing software, blogging platforms, online writing platforms, collaborative writing tools, and multimedia resources. As alternate forms of expression, encourage students to investigate podcasting, multimodal composition, and digital storytelling.

6. Encourage Critical Thinking and Reflection:

Encourage students to analyze, assess, and synthesize information from a variety of sources in order to foster critical thinking and reflection in writing instruction (Bean, 2011; Paul & Elder, 2008). Include writing assignments that force students to analyze difficult concepts, viewpoints, and cultural themes as well as to create arguments that are backed up by logic and facts. Students should be encouraged to evaluate their writing process, pinpoint their advantages and disadvantages, and make plans for their next writing projects.

In conclusion, teaching foreign languages in higher grades requires the development of written speech skills through a multifaceted approach that prioritizes the writing process, authentic tasks, language accuracy and fluency, model texts, technology integration, critical thinking, and reflection. Teachers can enable students to develop into proficient and self-assured writers in the target language by implementing these techniques and strategies into their lesson plans.

REFERENCES

1. Bean, J. C. (2011). *Engaging ideas: The professor's guide to integrating writing, critical thinking, and active learning in the classroom*. John Wiley & Sons.
2. Bygate, M. (2001). *Speaking*. In R. Carter & D. Nunan (Eds.), *The Cambridge guide to teaching English to speakers of other languages* (pp. 14-20). Cambridge University Press.
3. Ellis, R. (2008). *The study of second language acquisition* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press.
4. Flower, L., & Hayes, J. R. (1981). A cognitive process theory of writing. *College Composition and Communication*, 32(4), 365-387.
5. Hyland, K. (2003). *Second language writing*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Johns, A. M. (1997). *Text, role, and context: Developing academic literacies*. Cambridge University Press.
7. Levy, M., & Stockwell, G. (2006). *CALL dimensions: Options and issues in computer-assisted language learning*. Routledge.
8. Paul, R., & Elder, L. (2008). *Critical thinking: Tools for taking charge of your professional and personal life*. FT Press.
9. Swales, J. M. (1990). *Genre analysis: English in academic and research settings*. Cambridge University Press.